

Judicial Activism vis-à-vis Judicial Restraint Imperative for Delivering Justice: A Comparative Analysis

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Abstract

The well known maxim 'Ubi jus, ibi remedium – where there is a right there is a remedy' implicates that judges, in the absence of express provisions of law providing the remedy prayed for, ought not to ask the aggrieved to go back home and wait until the legislature enacts law providing remedy of such kind. Rather they will have to strive for discovering the remedy either by progressively interpreting the existing law or applying judicial discretion or inherent power so that the grievance of the justice-seeker does not remain unaddressed. This is because the legislatures cannot contemplate every situation that might arise in future. The judges, therefore, will have to be active in discharging their duties nurturing a pro-victim mind. Known as judicial activism, such kind of pro-people approach is imperative to ensure justice.

Key Words: Complete Justice, Constitutional Deviation, Inherent Power of the Courts, Judicial Review, Judicial Enforcement, Locus Standi, Legitimate Expectation, Separation of Judiciary and *Suo moto*.

1. Introduction

Judiciary is the safeguard to preserve and protect the constitution and to ensure the rights of the citizens. It has been entrusted with the responsibility to keep a vigilant eye to oversee whether the other organs of the state, i.e. the executive and the legislature are functioning within the ambit of the constitution. If the individual judges are not active and committed to discharge such duties with sincerity and integrity, then obviously the machinery of judiciary cannot protect the rights of the people. Hence, there must have efforts on the part of the judges to deliver justice to the larger sections of the people who are poor, illiterate, enslaved, deprived of the facilities to protect their rights and for various other reasons, unable to approach the court for redress though their constitutional and legal rights are violated or threatened. Such types of initiatives are termed as judicial activism. By dint of this doctrine, the judges can deliver justice to the door-steps of the really aggrieved and deserving people. However, judicial activism requires the judges to practice judicial self-restraint to maintain the sanctity of this extra-ordinary power as well

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as to check the capricious and arbitrary use of it so as to avert judicial autocracy. This article aims at depicting the real scenario of how actively the judiciary of Bangladesh is functioning in comparison to that of the USA, India and Pakistan as well as identifying the major challenges our judiciary is facing and the way out to overcome those.

2.1. Judicial Activism

Judicial activism is another new dimension to judicial review which means the court's authority to examine an executive or legislative act and to invalidate that act if it is contrary to the provisions of the constitution, the supreme law of the land. Evolved in the famous case, *Marbury v. Madison*¹, judicial review is considered in the United States, a key check on the powers of the other two branches of the government by the judiciary. The doctrine of 'judicial activism' refers to the situation when the judges broadly interpret the law in order to protect and ensure the public interest so that the people would not be deprived of their rights due to the lacunae of existing laws and legal mechanism. Black's Law Dictionary defines judicial activism as:²

"Judicial philosophy which motivates judges to depart from strict adherence to judicial precedent in favor of progressive and new social policies which are not always consistent with the restraint expect of appellate judges. It is commonly marked by decisions calling for social engineering and occasionally these decisions represent instrument into legislative and executive matters"

By scrutinizing the above definition, it can be pointed out that judicial activism connotes:

- i. that judges should come out from the traditional concept of strict adherence to the judicial precedent in interpreting the laws; and
- ii. that judges, while exercising judicial review, should interpret the laws keeping in mind the progressive and new socio-economic order.

In this sense, the philosophy of judicial activism is very much similar to the doctrine of complete justice which is enshrined in Article 104 of the constitution of the People's Republic of Bangladesh. In the case of *National Board of Revenue (NBR) vs. Nasrin Banu*³, complete justice has been defined as 'Sometimes it may be justice according to law, sometimes it may be justice according to fairness, equity and good conscience...justice tempered with mercy...it may be interference of an ordinary reasonable man.' Where social conditions and proprietary relations change but the law fails to change, the court will even then be required to settle the disputes before it and administer justice. In this situation the court will not ask the parties seeking justice to wait on Parliament for an appropriate law.⁴

2.2. Judicial Restraint

The opposite meaning of judicial activism is judicial restraint which means judges shall be continent in exercising power vested in them while deciding the issues before them. The term judicial restraint has been defined in Black's Law Dictionary as self imposed discipline by judges in deciding cases without permitting themselves to indulge their own personal views or ideas which may be inconsistent with existing decisional and statutory

¹ 5 US, 137 (1803).

² Black, Henry Campbell, *Black's Law Dictionary*, USA, West Publishing Company, 1979.

³ 48 DLR, (AD), 171.

⁴ See *Naziruddin vs. Hameeda Banu*, 45 DLR (AD) 44.

laws.⁵ In exercising judicial activism the court may pass any order to ensure complete justice but such an order must not be inconsistent with the constitution and the substantive provisions of the relevant laws of the country.⁶

2.3. Debate

Jurists are not in accord to unconditionally appreciate the concept of judicial activism. A strong argument in favor of this doctrine is that it tenders a scope to ensure and preserve a living constitution. In other words, the judiciary can play a vital role to keep the constitution up to date to deal with the ever changing society facing new socio-economic and political problems. The judiciary helps provide checks and balances and should grant itself an expanded role to counterbalance the effects of transient *majoritarianism* i.e., there should be an increase in the powers of a branch of government which is not directly subject to the electorate, so that the majority cannot dominate or oppress any particular minority through its elective powers⁷. The judges, by their reasoning and progressive interpretation make the constitution mass welfare oriented to keep pace with the emerging socio-economic context. In fact in many cases, it is a legitimate form of judicial review and obviously, while exercising the review power the judges will have to keep in mind that the interpretation of the law must change with the changing times. The critics, on the other hand, are in the opinion that judicial activism curtails the power of the elected legislative body which may hamper the rule of law and democracy⁸. If there is any shortcoming in the existing laws, it is the responsibility of the legislature, not the judiciary to cure the same. Even if there is any defect in the constitution, the responsibility to amend the defect lies in the legislature. In a leading case, Justice Waite said, ‘... while property clothed with a public interest entitled to compensation, it was for the legislature to decide what was reasonable ... for protection against legislative abuse, the people must turn to the polls, rather than the courts...’⁹.

Whatever argument may be against the concept of judicial activism, the doctrine has now become an important tool to uphold the right of the people. In a country with Anglo-American legal traditions, it is believed by many legal brains that “law is not what the law book says, but what the judges think it to be.”¹⁰

3.1. Practice of Judicial Activism in the United States of America

The origin of judicial activism can be traced from the judiciary of the United States of America (USA). In fact, it was born in 1804 in the United States of America when Chief Justice Marshall, the greatest Judge of the English-speaking world, decided *Marbury v. Madison*¹¹. Marbury was appointed Judge under the Judiciary Act of 1789 by the U.S. Federal Government. Though the warrant of appointment was signed it could not be delivered. Marbury brought an action for issue of a writ of mandamus. By then, Marshall became the Chief Justice of the Supreme Court having been appointed by the outgoing

⁵ Op. cit. Black, 1979.

⁶ See *Prem Chand Garg vs. Excise Commissioner*, AIR 1963 SC 996 (Para. 12).

⁷ Ely, John Hart, *Democracy and Distrust*, USA, Harvard University Press, 1980.

⁸ See Justice Antonin Scalia's dissenting opinion in *Romer v. Evans*; (*Romer, Governor of Colorado & others vs. Evans & others*, (94-1039), 517 U.S. 620 (1996).

⁹ *Munn vs. Illinois*, as quoted from Alfred Kelli & others, *The American constitution, its origin and Development*, 6th edition. New Delhi, Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Co. Ltd., 1986, p. 402.

¹⁰ Rahman, Dr. Mizanur, *Unveiling Democracy, State and Law*, 1st ed. Parama, Dhaka, 1999, p. 155.

¹¹ 5 U. S. 137 (1803).

President, who lost the election. Justice Marshall faced the imminent prospect of the Government not obeying the judicial fiat if the claim of Marbury was to be upheld. In a rare display of judicial statesmanship asserting the power of the Court to review the actions of the Congress and the Executive, Chief Justice Marshall declined the relief on the ground that Section 13 of the Judiciary Act of 1789, which was the foundation for the claim made by Marbury, was unconstitutional since it conferred in violation of the American Constitution, original jurisdiction on the Supreme Court to issue writs of mandamus. He observed that the Constitution was the fundamental and paramount law of the nation and it is for the court to say what the law is. He concluded that the particular phraseology of the Constitution of the United States confirms and strengthens the principle supposed to be essential to all written Constitutions. That a law repugnant to the Constitution is void and that the courts as well as other departments are bound by that instrument. If there was conflict between a law made by the Congress and the provisions in the Constitution, it was the duty of the court to enforce the Constitution and ignore the law. The twin concepts of judicial review and judicial activism were thus born.

During the period from 1898 to 1937, the U. S. Supreme Court declared 50 laws passed by the congress, and 400 enactments passed by the different states as unconstitutional. In *Roe vs. Wade*,¹² the Supreme Court gave a ruling decriminalizing abortion. The court struck down state laws banning abortion and ruled that such laws violated an implied right to privacy in the United States Constitution. In *Citizens United v. Federal Election Commission*,¹³ the Supreme Court declared the congressionally enacted limitations on corporate political spending and transparency as unconstitutional restrictions on free speech. In another case, *Perry v. Schwarzenegger*,¹⁴ the federal judges overturned California's constitutional amendment to ban same-sex marriage. However, the judiciary had to face challenges from the executive from time to time. For instance, President Ronald Regan in an address to his attorneys said that he was in favor of appointing as judges qualified and since persons who could understand that it would be a great danger to disrupt the election process curtailing the right of the suffrage of the people in the name of judicial activism.¹⁵ Similarly, Congressman Wally Herger reacted to the judgement of *Perry v. Schwarzenegger* that this was simply another example of judicial activism and legislating from the bench.¹⁶

3.2. Practice of Judicial Activism in India

The judiciary of India is one step ahead to exercise and flourish the doctrine of judicial activism as it for the first time formally recognized the doctrine of basic structure of the constitution in 1973. In fact, the concept of basic structure may be traced from the case of *Md. Abdul Haque vs. Fazlul Quader Chowdhury*,¹⁷ which was originated in the then

¹²1973, U.S. LEXIS, 159.(Roe v. Wade a classic example of judicial activism, The Daily Campus, September 12, 2008).

¹³ Stone, Geoffrey R. *Citizens United and Conservative Judicial Activism*, University of Illinois Law Review 2012 (2), p. 485.

¹⁴ 671 F.3d 1052.

¹⁵http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ronald_Reagan_Supreme_Court_candidates, last visited on January 12, 2014.

¹⁶Congressman Wally Herger issued a statement on August 4, 2010, "This is simply another example of judicial activism and legislating from the bench..."

¹⁷18 DLR, (SC), 69.

Dacca High Court but the doctrine for the first time stood in a firm footing when the Indian Supreme Court recognized the concept formally in *Kesavananda Bharati vs. State of Kerala*¹⁸. If we critically scrutinize some decisions delivered by the Supreme Court of India, it would be manifest that many issues were raised before the courts from time to time but the courts failed to redress them for either legal complexities or want of express provisions in the existing laws. This is because the court could not come out of the traditional concept of strict adherence of judicial precedent. In *Kasavananda Bharati* case, we witnessed the Indian judiciary to be very much active and creative when it declared the 24th Amendment of the Constitution partially void and ruled that the parliament could not destroy the basic structure of the constitution in exercising the amending power of the constitution. In *MC Mehta vs. Union of India*,¹⁹ the Supreme Court of India showed its boldness and creativity through the evolution of a new principle of ‘absolute liability’ which means responsibility for an injury can be imposed on the wrongdoer without proof of carelessness or fault. In this case, the court was dealing with the leakage of ileum gas on the 4th and 6th December, 1985 from one of the units of Shriram Foods and Fertilizers Industries in the city of Delhi claiming life of an advocate and injuring several others. The court had in mind that within one year, this was the second incident of large scale leakage of deadly gas in India as one year earlier, in Bhopal incident, more than 3000 people had died and lacs of others were subjected to serious diseases of various kinds. If the ‘Rule of strict liability’ as enumerated in *Ryland vs. Fletcher*,²⁰ was applied, the defendants who had established hazardous and inherently dangerous industries in and around thickly populated areas could have escaped the liability by virtue of the exceptions to this rule. Therefore, the court took a bold decision and held that it was not bound to follow the 19th century rule of English Law, and it could evolve a new rule suitable to the socio-economic conditions prevailing in India at the present day. Accordingly, the court evolved the ‘Rule of absolute liability’ which is subject to no exceptions.²¹

3.3. Practice of judicial activism in Pakistan

After the independence in 1947, Pakistan could not establish the actual democracy and rule of law; rather it has experienced several military regimes. Due to the naked interference by the military dictators, the judiciary could not stand on a firm footing even in the 21st century, the judiciary of Pakistan had to encounter another ordeal when the incumbent Chief Justice of the Supreme Court of Pakistan Iftikhar Mohammad Choudhury was fired by the former military dictator Parvej Mosarraf. However he was reinstated later as a result of a popular movement.²²

The judiciary of Pakistan faced its first challenge in 1955 when the Governor General dissolved the Constituent Assembly. The president of the Constituent Assembly challenged the action of the Governor General in Sind Chief Court²³ seeking the issuance

¹⁸ AIR, 1973 SC 1461.

¹⁹ AIR, 1987 SC 1086.

²⁰ L. R. 3 H. L. 330, (1868).

²¹ Bangia, R. K. *Law of Torts*, 5th edition, Allahabad Law Agency, Delhi, 2000, Pp. 357-359.

²² Iftikhar Mohammad Choudhury, the former Chief Justice of the Supreme Court of Pakistan, was dismissed by the then military dictator on March 9, 2007 and was restored by the democratically elected Government of Yusuf Raja Gilani on March 16, 2009.

²³ PLD, 1955, Sind, 96.

of mandamus and quo *warranto* under section 223A of the Government of India Act, 1935. The respondent pleaded that section 223A which gave the superior court to issue writs was, in the absence of the assent of the Governor General, not valid, and therefore, the court had no jurisdiction to issue writs to the respondents. The court unanimously held that the assent of the Governor was not necessary to the constitutional laws passed by the constituent assembly and as such section 223A was valid and enforceable without the assent of the Governor General. However in an appeal to the Federal Court, the Chief Justice Munir reversed the above decision and held that all Acts passed by the Constituent Assembly including the Acts providing for constitutional provisions required the assent of the Governor General for validity.²⁴

In this case, Munir, C. J. wanted to avoid direct confrontation with the clique without, of course, tarnishing the authority of the court. He in fact, tried to maintain a balance between the authority of the court and the stubborn attitude of the executive²⁵. With the effect of the above decision, 44 constitutional Acts became invalid for want of assent of the Governor General. Then the Governor General issued the Emergency Power Ordinance, 1955 with a view to validating 35 of the Acts retrospectively. The above ordinance was challenged in the case of *Usif Patel vs. the Crown*,²⁶ and the Federal Court after examining the Ordinance, held that the Governor General could not, by ordinance, validate any of the laws which had become invalid for want of his assent. In the above case, the court had been able to restrain the Governor General from exercising the constituent power and made him submit to the court seeking its advice in tiding over the crisis.

Another challenge was faced by the Supreme Court of Pakistan when the validity of the Laws Continuance (Enforcement) Order, 1958²⁷ was challenged in the case of *State vs. Dosso*²⁸. In this case, the court could not show sufficient judicial prudence; rather gave the validity of the proclamation of Martial Law on the doctrine of 'efficacy and successful revolution.' This decision was strongly criticized that the court misused the positivist theory of efficacy propounded by Hans Keelson.²⁹

However, in the case of *Miss. Asma Jilani vs. the Government of Punjab*,³⁰ the Supreme Court showed its boldness by overruling the decision of *State vs. Dosso* and held the military takeover as illegal. In this case, Hamoodur Rahman, C.J. observed that the principle enunciated in *State vs. Dosso* was wholly unacceptable and it could not be treated as good law either on the principle of *stare decisis* or even otherwise. Though the court, in the above case, condoned certain acts done during the regime on the basis of necessity but it did not legitimize those acts as Hamoodur Rahman, C.J. observed, 'I would call this a principle of condonation and not legitimization.'

²⁴ Federation of Pakistan Vs. Moulavi Tamizuddin Khan, PLD, FC, 240.

²⁵ See Chowdhury, Z. I., *The Role of Judiciary in the Constitutional Development of Pakistan (1947 – 1971)*, The Dhaka University Studies, Part – F, Vol – 1, No. 1, 1990, at Pp. 1 – 24.

²⁶ PLD, 1955, FC, 387.

²⁷ President's Order (Post proclamation) No. 1 of 1958.

²⁸ PLD 1958 SC 533.

²⁹ See Kelson, Hans, *General Theory of Law and State*, Anderson Wedberg, Harvard University Press, 1946.

³⁰ PLD 1972 SC 139.

Similarly, in the case of *Begum Nusrat Bhutto vs. Chief of Army Staff and others*,³¹ the Supreme Court following the *Asma Jilani*'s case, refused to validate the military rule on the basis of its effectiveness, and termed the 'abrupt political change' on the plea of which Martial Law was declared in 1977, as merely a case of 'constitutional deviation' which amounted to no valid ground to validate Martial Law.

The present judiciary of Pakistan under Chief Justice Iftikhar Muhammad Chaudhury is very active to uphold the rule of law and democratic practices in Pakistan which is beset with internal terrorist activities and the US drone attack across the Afghan border. Very recently the contempt of court proceeding against the government in the National Reconciliation Order (NRO) implementation case and the disqualification of Pakistani Prime Minister Yusuf Raza Gilani by the Supreme Court of Pakistan chief justice Iftikhar Muhammad Chaudhury is the rarest example of exercising judicial activism. On December 16, 2009, the Supreme Court of Pakistan issues a petition to consider NRO 2007 to be null and void which provided immunity to the offenders of law, including money launderers and embezzlers.³² The ordinance was drafted and approved by President Pervez Musharraf. The court asked the National Accountability Bureau (NAB) to reopen the cases against the incumbent President Asif Ali Zardari entailing the Swiss scam. However, the allegation was out rightly denied by the Prime Minister Yusuf Raja Gilani which led to his disqualification for contempt of court.

After comparing the decisions of *State vs. Dosso* with that of *Asma Jilani and Nusrat Bhutto*, it can be clearly perceived that what might happen to the rule of law if the judiciary is not active; rather biased and submissive to the external pressure!

3.4. Practice of Judicial Activism in Bangladesh

The judiciary of Bangladesh made a sound constitutional journey in 1972 after a nine-month bloody war of liberation but unfortunately, its path was not always smooth as the constitutionalism in the newly emerged country had frequently been obstructed due to subsequent amendments to the constitution. The ruling authority always tried to keep the judiciary under control. However, the contributions of judiciary are many. Evolution of Public Interest Litigation (PIL), basic structure theory of the constitution and principle of legitimate expectation, application of the principles of prospective overruling, separation of judiciary from the executive organ of the state are the outcome of judicial activism practiced by our judges.

3.4.1. Public Interest Litigation (PIL)

The judiciary of Bangladesh has showed its sufficient maturity when it for the first time recognized the concept of Public Interest Litigation (PIL) in Bangladesh in the famous case of *Kazi Mukhlesur Rahman vs. Bangladesh*³³ popularly known as *Berubari* case. In this case the court recognized the *locus standi* to the concerned person apart from the persons directly aggrieved. In law, *locus standi* means the right to bring an action, to be heard in court, or to address the Court on a matter before it. It was held that 'It appears to be that the question of *locus standi* does not involve the court's jurisdiction to hear a person but of the competency of the person to claim a hearing, so the question is one

³¹ PLD 1977 SC 657.

³² http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/National_Reconciliation_Ordinance, last accessed on 12.11.2013.

³³ 26 DLR AD 44.

discretion which the court exercises upon due consideration to the facts and circumstances.³⁴ Since the *Berubari case*, the PIL concept has now become an established rule through several judicial pronouncements like *Dr. Mohiuddin Farooque vs. Bangladesh*³⁵ popularly known as FAP 20 case. In FAP 20 case, it was declared that in the constitution of Bangladesh which is autochthonous³⁶ in nature, the people are the ultimate holders of power. Accordingly, social and economic justice issues must have primacy over special or individual interests. Thus in cases of public wrong or injury, any member of the public can file a writ petition on behalf of the entire public or a particular vulnerable section of the society.

3.4.2. Basic Structure of the Constitution

The concept of basic structure of the constitution was unknown to the constitutional practice of Bangladesh until 1989. In a country like Bangladesh where the ruling political parties having absolute majority in the parliament do not hesitate to amend the constitution to serve their own interest, the existence of such principle is very important to avert arbitrary amendment to the constitution. In the case of *Anwar Hossain Choudhury vs. Bangladesh*³⁷ popularly known as the Constitution 8th Amendment case, the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court took a mile stone decision to establish the doctrine of basic structure in the constitution through a new and progressive interpretation of Article 142 of the constitution. The same has been possible for the merit and creativity of the learned judges concerned as well as the relentless perseverance of the lawyers.

3.4.3. Legitimate Expectation

A person is said to have a legitimate expectation when he/she reasonably believes that he/she is entitled to a particular right.³⁸ Of course, such belief will arise out of the action of the authority. Thus a promise made in the shape of a statement of policy or a procedure regularly adopted by the authority may give rise to what is called legitimate expectation, that is, expectation of a kind which the court now enforces.³⁹ It gives the applicant sufficient *locus standi* for judicial review.

In *Bangladesh Soya-Protein Project Ltd. vs. Secretary, Ministry of MDMR*,⁴⁰ the government initiated 'School Feeding Programme' and entered into contract with the petitioner for supply of soya-protein biscuits to schools for a fixed period. On the expiry of the contract period, the government discontinued the programme. The High Court Division held that such discontinuance of the programme, violating its own policy, was in gross violation of the legitimate expectation not only of the petitioner but also of the millions of under-nourished children warranting interference of the court and directed the government to implement its policy decision.

³⁴ Ibid.

³⁵ 50 DLR (1998) 85.

³⁶ An Autochthonous Constitution means literally 'aboriginal' indicating that the legal continuity with the Former Power was severed and the Constitution was enacted by a Constitutional Assembly of the newly independent state as in the USA after the American Revolution.

³⁷ BLD, 1989 (Spl. Issue).

³⁸ Naziruddin vs. Hameeda Banu, 45 DLR, (AD), P. 38; Raziul Hassan vs. Badruzzaman Khan and others, 48 DLR, (AD), P. 71.

³⁹ Islam, Mahmudul, *The Constitutional Laws of Bangladesh*, Dhaka, Mullick Brothers, 2012.

⁴⁰ 6 BLC 681.

Though criticized very sharply, the above decision bears the testimony to the creativity of the judges to protect and promote the interest of the millions of under-nourished children.

3.4.4. Prospective Overruling

Prospective overruling which was originated in the USA signifies that a ruling of the court will be effective in future from such date as directed by the court and not from the past. In the Constitution 8th Amendment Case,⁴¹ the Supreme Court did not struck down the acts done under the amended Article 100 and so in *Bangladesh Italian Marble Works Limited vs. Government of Bangladesh and others*⁴² popularly known as the Constitution 5th Amendment Case, the HCD condoned all activities done under the 5th Amendment Act, 1979 as ‘transaction past and closed’ by applying the principle of prospective overruling.

In the constitution thirteenth Amendment case,⁴³ the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court prospectively declared the Constitution Thirteenth (Amendment) Act, 1996 which provides the provision of Care Taker Government as null and void. The court also observed that next two parliamentary elections may be held under the Care Taker Government.

3.4.5. Enforceability of the Fundamental Principle of State Policy

Since the very inception of the constitutional journey, it has been a debatable issue whether the Fundamental Principles of State Policy (FPSP) enshrined in Part II of the Constitution of the People’s Republic of Bangladesh should be judicially enforceable or not as article 8(2) of the constitution categorically provides that these principles shall not be judicially enforceable. In *Kudrat -e- Elahi Panir vs. Bangladesh*,⁴⁴ the enforceability of the FPSP was raised, but the Appellate Division of the Supreme Court decided the case on a separate ground leaving the issue of enforceability unsettled because it was not the main issue of the case. Nonetheless, some important principles regarding the enforceability of the FPSP have been enunciated from the case. In the High Court Division, Naimuddin Ahmed, J. discussed the enforceability of the FPSP hypothetically, and Mustafa Kamal, J. in the Appellate Division impliedly recognized the enforceability of the FPSP as he observed, ‘...is the High Court Division in its writ jurisdiction the only light at the end of the tunnel?’ B. H. Choudhury, J. in the 8th Amendment case⁴⁵ observed, ‘though the directive principles are not enforceable by any court...the endeavor of the Government must be to realize these aims and not to whittle them down.’

Given the above judicial pronouncements, it is now manifest that though the Fundamental Principles of State Policy are not enforceable by the judiciary, nonetheless, the government is under constitutional obligation to implement, and not to violate, these principles gradually subject to its limited wealth and resources; and the judiciary has the constitutional mandate to keep a vigilant eye if the government is discharging its constitutional obligation. For instance, the Supreme Court, in the case of *Secretary, Ministry of Finance, Government of Bangladesh vs. Mr. Md. Masdar Hossain and*

⁴¹ Op. cit. BLD (1989).

⁴² 14 BLD (2006) (Spl. Issue).

⁴³ Civil Appeal No. 139 of 2005 with Civil Petition for Leave to Appeal No. 596 of 2005; available at www.supremecourt.gov.bd/scweb/documents/526214_13thAmet.pdf.

⁴⁴ 44 DLR (AD) 319.

⁴⁵ Op. cit. BLD (1989).

*others*⁴⁶ directed the government to ensure the separation of the lower judiciary from the executive of organ of the state. But the government delayed to implement the directions taking time from the courts. At last, in 2007, the caretaker government took initiatives to implement the judgment by promulgating two ordinances⁴⁷ and by making four service rules namely (a) Bangladesh Judicial Service Commission Rules, 2007, (b) Bangladesh Judicial Service (Pay Commission) Rules 2007, (c) Bangladesh Judicial Service Commission (Constitution of Service, Appointments in the Service and Suspension, Removal & Dismissal from the Service) Rules, 2007 and (d) Bangladesh Judicial Service (Posting, Promotion, Grant of Leave, Control, Discipline and other Condition of Service) Rules, 2007. The present government in 2009 amended the Code of Criminal Procedure 1898⁴⁸ which formally removed the impediments to the separation of the lower judiciary from executive control and in the appointment of judicial magistrates. The separation of judiciary has been contemplated in Article 22 of the constitution which is, as per Article 8(2), if literally interpreted, not judicially enforceable. But the implication of Masder Hossain case indicates that the court technically enforced Article 22 by compelling the government to take initiatives for the separation of lower judiciary, as Latifur Rahman, J. later on Chief Justice of Bangladesh, observed, ‘though more than 29 years have elapsed since making of the constitution and coming into force, no effective steps have been taken to separate the judiciary from the executive organ of the state.’

4. Scope of Judicial Activism in Bangladesh

The existing laws leave an ample opportunity for the judges to be active in dispensation of justice as we frequently see provisions like ‘*suo moto*’, ‘as he thinks fit,’ in the procedural laws of our country. *Suo motu*, a Latin legal term, means ‘on its own motion.’ While ‘as he thinks fit’ implies the wide discretion of the judges to decide a matter before him/ her on the basis of equity, justice and conscience and applying judicial mind.

Very specifically, Article 104 of the constitution of the People’s Republic of Bangladesh empowers the Appellate Division to issue such directions, orders, decrees or writs as may be necessary for doing complete justice⁴⁹ in any cause or matter pending before it, including orders for the purpose of securing the attendance of any person or the discovery or production of any document. Section 561A of the Code of Criminal Procedure, 1898, saves the inherent power of the High Court Division of the Supreme Court of Bangladesh. By exercising its inherent power, the High Court Division can make such orders as may be necessary-

- i. to give effect to any order under the Code, or
- ii. to prevent abuse of the process of any Court, or
- iii. to secure the ends of justice.

Similarly, section 151 of the Code of Civil Procedure, 1908 saves the inherent power of the civil courts.

⁴⁶ 20 BLD (2000) 104.

⁴⁷ Ordinance No. II and IV of 2007.

⁴⁸ See the Act No. XXXII of 2009.

⁴⁹ It is an extraordinary power given to the highest court of the land which is to be exercised sparingly and in exceptional circumstances to remove manifest and undoubted injustice.

By ‘inherent power of the court’ it is meant such powers that the court enjoys by virtue of being a court to regulate proceedings before it including punishing contempt. Law does not confer any new power on the courts but merely saves their powers to make such decision as may be necessary for the ends of justice or to prevent abuse of the process of the courts. Therefore, it can easily be perceived that in many cases, the redress of the parties who are comparatively on a weak footing than their opponent parties depends on how the judges concerned exercise their judicial discretion.

In comparison to lower judiciary, the judges of our higher judiciary seem to be very much active in exercising judicial activism in administration of justice. Judicial activism on the part of judges of the Supreme of Court of Bangladesh was found to be exercised in 1992⁵⁰ when a Division Bench constituted with two judges of the High Court Division, on the basis of a newspaper report, issued a *suo moto* rule on the Deputy Commissioner of Satkhira and others⁵¹ to show cause as to why the detinue Md. Nazrul Islam should not be brought before the court to be dealt with in accordance with law and also to show cause under what authority he was being detained. The said detinue, Nazrul Islam was in custody since 1977 when he was a boy of nine years old in connection with 12 criminal cases. In some cases, he was ether acquitted or his sentence expired and in other cases no charge sheet was submitted. The HC court bench held that the detention of the *detinue* in custody was absolutely illegal, void *ab anitio* and without jurisdiction. The court therefore, directed that the said detinue be set at large.

In *Daily Star and Prothom-alo vs. State*,⁵² a Division Bench of the High Court Division of the Supreme Court, took cognizance on the basis of newspaper report that the Public Prosecutor (PP) was delaying the trial and the accused police personnel had been putting pressure on the wife of the victim not to proceed with the case. The court accordingly issued a *suo moto* rule on the Deputy Commissioner of Dhaka to show cause as to why the Public Prosecutor should not be changed.

The aforesaid instances depict that if the judges are active and committed to perform their constitutional and legal duties with sincerity and integrity, justice will reach to the door-steps of every citizen and nobody will be deprived of their rights of access to proper justice due to inability either financial or political, to move to the court.

5. Limitations

To cultivate judicial activism, an efficient and independent judicial mechanism is imperative. But our judiciary is encountering many challenges to flourish itself as a creative and an independent institution. These challenges are of two folds, i.e. shortcomings in the existing laws and political interference. Bangladesh still does not have a legislation prescribing detailed 'qualifications' for the appointment of judges to the Supreme Court. Despite requirement in Article 95(2) (c)⁵³ and a recommendation in the landmark judgment in *Idrisur Rahman v Bangladesh*,⁵⁴ for making law specifying

⁵⁰Haque, Kazi Ebadul, *Administration of Justice in Bangladesh*, 2nd edition, Dhaka, Asiatic Society of Bangladesh, 2006, P. 229.

⁵¹ State vs. the Deputy Commissioner of Satkhira and others, 45 DLR, 643.

⁵² 53 DLR, 155.

⁵³ The Constitution of the Peoples' Republic of Bangladesh, 1972 available at <http://bdlaws.minlaw.gov.bd/>.

⁵⁴ 60 DLR (2008)714.

appointment guidelines, the government has yet to enact such legislation. Article 95 of the Constitution of Bangladesh provides for the appointment of judges to the Supreme Court. It requires that a person cannot be qualified for appointment as a judge unless he or she is a citizen of Bangladesh and has practiced law in the Supreme Court for at least ten years, or has held judicial office in the country for at least ten years, or has other such qualifications as may be 'prescribed by law'. In the absence of a legislation prescribing detailed qualification, the 'at least ten years' experience as a lawyer or judicial officer appears as a broad criterion, leaving scope for political influences in selection and appointment of judges to the Supreme Court.

Moreover, the governments are very interested to take the advantage of Article 98 of the constitution. Under this Article, judges are first appointed on *ad hoc* basis and then made permanent. As a result, the judges might be tempted to be influenced in his decisions in favour of the authorities to satisfy the governments to make it sure that his appointment will be made permanent. Further, by an amendment to Article 99 in 1977, the retired judges of the Supreme Court were allowed to be appointed in a judicial or quasi judicial office which is considered to be a major hindrance to the practice of judicial activism. In 2008, during the tenure of the Caretaker Government, an ordinance named the Supreme Judicial Commission Ordinance 2008 was promulgated which specifies procedures for the appointment of judges to both the Appellate Division and the High Court Division of the Supreme Court. But it was later on repealed. On 6 June, 2010 the High Court asked the government to explain in six weeks why specific guidelines should not be framed for appointment of judges to bring transparency and competitiveness in the process. Two years have since passed and the government has yet to pass or even draft or provide for public discussion a law formulating guidelines for appointment of judges to the Supreme Court.⁵⁵ Without framing guidelines, the present government has appointed more than 50 judges in the High Court divisions since coming to power.

The Law Commission recently recommended that the government pass a law allowing appointment of legal experts from different professions as Supreme Court judges.⁵⁶ According to the recommendation, not only practical experience but also in-depth knowledge and understanding of the vast theory, explanation and use of law, and perfect perception of justice are required to conduct judicial work.

6. Conclusion

Judicial activism is undisputedly said to be the prerequisite for ensuring a free and fair society under the rule of law. As judiciary is the last resort where the aggrieved people move in, it is the sacred duty of the judges to cultivate a creative and judicious mind in order to make it sure that people are not deprived of remedy either for legal complexities or for absence of specific provisions of law. As we see above, in the absence of a strong institutional basis, the rate of exercising judicial activism by the judges fluctuates to a great extent in different situations. Therefore, it is emergent that the machinery of the judiciary be let run in a way where judicial activism will be practiced not by the individual but by the collective initiatives. To this end, judiciary should be kept beyond the outside interference by introducing a transparent mode of appointing judges as it is required by the constitution.

⁵⁵ The Daily Independent, *Judges appointment rules yet to be framed*, 04 September 2013, p. 1.

⁵⁶ Ibid, 08 May, 2012.

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